

SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PREVENTION, TREATMENT MEASURES AND METHODS OF DENTAL DISEASES IN YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the prevention, treatment and measures of dental diseases in young people. It contains important practical recommendations for early detection, treatment and prevention of dental diseases in young people. In addition, information is given on the basis of examples and analysis about the fact that young people regularly undergo a dental check-up, have a healthy lifestyle, follow proper nutrition and hygiene rules.

НЕКОТОРЫЕ СООБРАЖЕНИЯ О ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ, МЕРАХ И МЕТОДАХ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ СТОМАТОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ У МОЛОДЫХ ЛЮДЕЙ

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ABSTRACT

В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы профилактики, лечения и мер профилактики стоматологических заболеваний у лиц молодого возраста. В ней даны важные практические рекомендации по раннему выявлению, лечению и профилактике стоматологических заболеваний у лиц молодого возраста. Кроме того, на примерах и анализе дана информация о том, что молодые люди регулярно проходят стоматологический осмотр, ведут здоровый образ жизни, соблюдают правила правильного питания и гигиены.

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ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada yoshlarda uchraydigan tish kasalliklari profilaktikasi, davolash usullari va choralari xususida fikr yuritilgan. Unda yoshlarda uchraydigan tish kasallarini erta aniqlash, davolash va oldini olish bo'yicha muhim amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan. Bundan tashqari yoshlarning stomatolog ko'rigidan doimiy ravishda o'tishlari, sog'lom turmush tarzi, to'g'ri ovqatlanish va gigiyena qoidalari to'g'ri amal qilishlari borasida misollar va tahlillar asosida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Modern studies have proven the commonality of many risk factors for somatic and dental pathologies [13, 7, 4]. The development of caries is caused by 2 groups of factors: "... the first group includes those factors that cause damage to dental tissues - dental plaque, easily digestible carbohydrates, the composition and functions of saliva, and the second group includes characteristics that are not directly involved in the development of caries: socio-economic factors, dental diseases in the past and general somatic pathology" [2]. The frequency of dental pathologies is partly due to climatic and geographical features of residence, behavioral factors, hygiene culture and education of the individual, balanced diet and regimen, medical activity. Stress also contributes to the development of chronic periodontitis [1,4,6].

Goleva N.A. writes: "...changes in behavioral stereotypes of the majority of student youth towards deterioration, especially in men, contribute to a decrease in the level of oral health, these include: unhealthy diet (54.6%), poor oral hygiene (20.0%), smoking (25.1%), irregular visits (90.6%) and avoiding visiting the dentist when there is pain (50.6%)" [2,9].

According to Protsenko A.S.: "... nutrition is of particular importance at a young age for the formation, maintenance and strengthening of dental health, the nature and regimen of nutrition determine the adequacy of the structure of hard dental tissues" [8].

Lutskaya I.K. believes: "...hard natural food has a good effect, as it activates the self-cleaning mechanism of the teeth, biting and chewing mechanically cleans the surfaces, abundant salivation washes away food residues". Consumption of rough natural food reduces the frequency of all dental lesions [3,5].

The protective role of saliva in the prevention of caries is stated by Borovsky E.V.: "...thanks to saliva, control is exercised over the microflora of the oral cavity, the removal of pathogenic agents both mechanically and due to enzyme and buffer systems, as well as antibacterial components (lysozyme, lipase, amylase, immunoglobulins, etc.)". This point of view is shared by Nikolaev A.I.: "...not only the influence of oral fluid components on plaque accumulation is noted, but also the amount of secreted secretion; individuals with reduced secretion are more susceptible to caries" [8,11,14].

Research by Redinova T.A. established: "...in patients with moderate and high degrees of oral dysbiosis, the intensity of caries and the severity of inflammatory periodontal diseases are 40-50% higher."

Zyuzkina S.A. noted a close relationship between caries and periodontitis with the duration and severity of somatic pathology. Kolesnikov E.A. noted a high prevalence of caries in children with chronic gastrointestinal and cardiovascular pathologies [4,12].

Dmitrieva L.A. established: "... chronic periodontal diseases, tooth loss and systemic osteoporosis have common pathogenetic mechanisms, which consist of disturbances in mineral metabolism and bone tissue resorption" [9].

Gunko M.V. questions the relationship between systemic osteoporosis and the state of the oral cavity [5].

Failure to comply with oral hygiene rules causes a constant increase in dental pathologies. The high frequency of occurrence and high intensity of periodontal diseases and dental caries predetermines the need to study the level of oral hygiene in students.

The above data lead to the conclusion that a single adequate position on the influence of exogenous and endogenous factors in the development of dental pathology and their interactions has not yet been developed. The cult of a healthy lifestyle is not yet universally cultivated and widespread among young people [16,10].

All the described and discussed risk factors are also present to some extent among the youth of our country and have an adverse effect on the health of young people, both somatic and dental. Prevention of common dental diseases is generally recognized as the most important and pressing problem of dentistry at the present stage of its development [6,12].

The basis of prevention is considered to be: "... eliminating the causes of the occurrence and development of diseases, as well as creating conditions for increasing the body's resistance to the effects of unfavorable environmental factors" [13,24]. The relevance of research in the field of prevention of oral mucosa and dental pathologies is associated with the ubiquity and intensity of their diseases, and the low efficiency of the preventive measures used [17].

Dental health is based on the requirement: "... only through the introduction into everyday practice of programs and methods for the prevention of dental diseases, specially adapted for each social stratum of society" [19,23].

Prevention of dental diseases is aimed at: "improving the hygienic condition of the oral cavity, including dental education, thorough controlled tooth cleaning and professional hygienic treatment of teeth, the correct choice of hygiene products and the use of various means in order to increase the caries resistance of teeth" [29,26].

Preventive measures include the correct selection of toothpastes and the necessary frequency of tooth brushing, professional care of tooth enamel and widespread dental education of the population [25,8].

The most effective preventive measures are considered to be: "... professional oral hygiene, including training in oral hygiene rules, monitoring their implementation, constant motivation of the patient during treatment; measures aimed at preventing and eliminating dental plaque, observing personal hygiene rules, rational nutrition, hygienic propaganda and education of the population" [27]. The activity and responsibility of the patients themselves in maintaining and monitoring their own health is also mandatory [15, 28]. Pathogenetic prevention of dental diseases includes a certain set of specific measures and manipulations: "... fluoride prophylaxis, remineralizing therapy, endogenous caries prevention, sealing of dental fissures" [23,31].

To improve the level of dental health, various public preventive programs are used, introduced and applied by many countries [28]. Student youth: "... this is a special social group of the population, united by certain age limits, intensive mental work in the process of professional training, specific learning conditions, lifestyle and mentality at the age of 16 to 25 years, for the preservation of whose health a well-established system of prevention and structure of medical care are of no small importance" [32,30]. The protection of youth health unconditionally depends on sanitary-hygienic, sanitary-epidemiological and medical well-being.

Only a few programs for the prevention of dental pathology have been published in the available literature [31,29]. Improving the quality of life of students by introducing measures to prevent common dental pathology is undoubtedly relevant and necessary.

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